

A Novel Hybrid Multiobjective Starfish – White Shark Optimization Routing Algorithm for Sustainable 6G-IoMT Healthcare Systems

Padma Priya A¹

Assistant Professor

Department of Computer Science and Engineering

SSM Institute of Engineering and Technology

Dindigul, India

ssmcsepadmapriyaa@gmail.com

Ananthi G²

Associate Professor

Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering

Thiagarajar College of Engineering

Madurai, India

gananthi@tce.edu

Received: 22nd Oct 2025 / Accepted : 29th Oct 2025 ,

© ICIAET 2025

Abstract— The rapid development of sixth-generation (6G) wireless communication is predicted to transform the Internet of Medical Things (IoMT) by allowing for ultra-low latency, massive connections, and high-reliability healthcare services. The high energy consumption and short battery life of 6G and IoMT devices could make it difficult to maintain efficient, seamless connectivity. This paper introduces a proposed energy-efficient routing protocol, namely Hybrid Multi-objective Starfish – White Shark Optimization-based Cluster Head Selection Algorithm (HMO-SF-WSO). Although the Starfish optimizer has excellent search and application strategies, it may encounter difficulties across various types of applications, particularly in tasks such as cluster head selection. To boost the exploitation and exploration phase of the star fish optimizer, we integrate the white shark optimization algorithm's fish schooling behavior. Clearly, most contemporary strategies employ static IoMT deployments and do not involve multi-hop inter-cluster communication. To conquer these limitations, mobility-based node deployment and multi-hop inter-cluster communication schemes have been introduced to improve scalability and reliability in 6G-enabled networks. Experimental outcomes show that our proposed routing mechanism consumes 27.5% less energy than other baseline approaches.

Keywords— Cluster Head Selection, Energy Efficiency, Internet of Medical Things, HMO-SF-WSO, Optimization Algorithm

I. INTRODUCTION

The IoMT is now recognized as a key component of next-generation healthcare systems, enabling continuous patient monitoring, real-time transmission of medical data, and remote diagnosis[1]. Nevertheless, the rising density of IoMT nodes and the stringent requirements for ultra-low latency, high security, and energy efficiency pose substantial

hurdles for current wireless communication methods. Sixth-generation (6G) [2] wireless networks are expected to address these difficulties by providing higher data speeds, intelligent networking, greater connectivity, and ultra-reliable low-latency communication. Developing efficient and energy-conscious networking solutions for 6G-enabled IoMT [3] [4] [5] systems has emerged as a research priority.

In general, there are 2 types of network architecture in these IoT or IoMT, homogeneous and heterogeneous networks [6]. In a homogeneous network, all the nodes hold the same initial energy, and in a heterogeneous network, the nodes hold different initial energies. The two-level heterogeneous network has two initial values. 50% of the nodes have 1.0J while 50% have 1.5J. Similarly, a three-level heterogeneous network has two ranges of initial values: 50% nodes with 1.0J, 30% nodes with 1.5J, and 20% nodes with 2.0J. Typically, 6G-enabled IoMT networks operate in high-mobility architectures due to the dynamic mobility of medical equipment, patients, and mobile healthcare infrastructure. Recently, [7] [8] have used a heterogeneous network to establish a 6G-enabled IoMT configuration; However, these techniques are restricted to the deployment of a fixed node or to the absence of multi-hop cluster-head communication. To address the drawbacks of the current approach, we introduced mobility nodes and multi-hop cluster-head communication. Additionally, we proposed a hybrid Multi-objective Starfish–White Shark Optimization-based Cluster Head Selection energy-efficient routing Algorithm.

Recently, a few studies have employed cluster-head selection-based energy-efficient routing algorithms to advance network lifetime in 6G-enabled IoMT nodes. On the other hand, traditional methods have been used by various studies, such as LEACH [9], HEED [10], as well as optimization-based methods, for energy-efficient routing in IoT networks. For both IoT and IoMT system clustering, head selection based on optimization offers a significant improvement over the conventional routing algorithm.

Conventional approaches often make probabilistic or local choices that might not yield the best CH placement. Optimization-based techniques explore the entire global search space, increasing the likelihood of finding cluster heads closer to the optimal state and improving overall network performance.

Our proposed HMO-SF-WSO routing algorithm is motivated by two optimization algorithms: the Starfish Optimization Algorithm (SFOA) [11] and the White Shark Optimization (WSO) [12]. The starfish optimizer is a bio-inspired optimization algorithm developed to resolve engineering optimization problems. It imitates the prey-finding, exploration, and regeneration behaviors of starfish. It has two main stages: exploitation and exploration. To boost search capacity and computational efficiency, the exploration phase uses a hybrid search pattern that combines unidimensional and five-dimensional search strategies to mimic the exploratory behavior of starfish. During the exploitation phase, the algorithm mimics starfish predation and regeneration movements using a two-directional search and adaptive movement, thereby improving local exploitation and accelerating convergence. The Starfish Algorithm exhibits strong exploitation and good exploration, but when applied to tasks such as cluster head selection and feature selection, it may struggle to balance these mechanisms. To advance the exploitation and exploration performance of starfish, we have adopted the white shark fish schooling behavior. Generally, sharks can change their location to the one that offers the best position, which is very near the prey. The sharks' final location may be somewhere in the search area closest to the ideal prey. WSO mixes fish school behavior with leader-following shark movement to boost exploration and exploitation performances. Inspired by white sharks' effective schooling behavior, these principles inform the proposed starfish optimization algorithm to boost exploitation and exploration efficiency for effective clustering-based head selection.

The remaining part of the study is organized as follows: a comprehensive review of related work is provided in Section 2. System models presented in Section 3. The proposed hybrid multi-objective Starfish–White shark optimization cluster head selection algorithm is discussed in Section 4. Section 5 discusses the performance analysis of the proposed methodology. Section 6 discusses the conclusion and future work details.

II. RELATED WORKS

This part discusses new studies on the integration of the IoMT with 5G/6G networks, focusing on cluster-head selection-based routing methods. Many studies utilized several clustering algorithms to enhance network lifetime and energy-efficient communication in IoMT. Of these, most focused on optimization-based algorithms for cluster head selection.

The study [13] utilized an improved bifold cuckoo search algorithm-based cluster-head-selection technique to improve the network lifetime in IoMT. Another study [14] used an ant colony optimization-based clustering routing protocol to improve network stability by combining a centroid-based technique with the cluster-head-selection protocol. In [15], a dual-cluster-head-selection technique was used to ensure fault tolerance and load balancing; a genetic algorithm was used for Energy-Efficient Routing. The OptiGeA protocol

[16] used different factors, such as density, energy, distance, and heterogeneous nodes' capacities, for cluster head selection.

Prior work mostly focuses on energy-efficient routing protocols to enhance IoMT quality of service; however, these strategies do not account for the possibility of packet loss, which directly affects energy consumption. Study [17] addressed these limitations and proposed a whale-optimized cluster-head selection algorithm to improve IoMT quality of service, accounting for packet-loss probability. Some studies have integrated a deep learning algorithm for cluster head selection. [18] proposed a deep learning-based Manta Ray Foraging Optimization (MRFO) method for multi-objective cluster head (CH) selection. The multi-objective fitness function was formulated to optimize energy consumption, traffic density, end-to-end delay, and communication distance.

Recently, a study [7] presented Artificial Democratic Cuckoo Glowworm Remora Optimization-based cluster-head-selection for 6G networks and also provided a lightweight blockchain mechanism for secure data transmission. It performed better, increasing network lifetime by 27% compared to basic protocols such as HEED and LEACH. Another study [8] utilized a novel hybrid greylag goose-based optimized clustering (HGGOC) method for cluster head selection. It used the Levy flight mechanism to optimize Cluster head selection and achieved 64% improvement in network stability and a 47% increase in node lifetime compared to existing approaches.

Nevertheless, these current methods are limited by their reliance on static IoMT deployments and the absence of multi-hop inter-cluster communication. To address these limitations, mobility-based node deployment and a multi-hop inter-cluster communication scheme are introduced to enhance scalability and reliability in 6G-enabled networks. Additionally, to enhance network stability and quality of service, this study proposes a hybrid multi-objective starfish-white shark optimization-based cluster head selection algorithm.

III. SYSTEM MODELS

In this study, 6G-enabled IoMT device deployment-based monitoring scenarios were established. Previous studies mostly used static IoMT devices and lacked multi-hop cluster-head communication. Generally, 6G networks support the mobility of IoMT devices; therefore, this study focuses on mobility-aware operational scenarios. Additionally, this work introduces multi-hop inter-cluster communication, replacing direct base-station-to-cluster-head communication, thereby enhancing scalability and reliability in 6G-enabled networks. To our knowledge, previous research on IoMT-based 6G networks has not utilized mobility or multi-hop cluster-head communication.

Furthermore, as mentioned in [5], this study used a 3-level heterogeneous network architecture comprising three node types: normal, intermediate, and advanced. Normally, 6G-enabled devices have varying initial energy levels. Consequently, these three-stage multi-hop network nodes have distinct initial energy levels, such as 2.0J, 1.5J, and 1.0J for advanced, intermediate, and normal nodes, respectively. The MATLAB environment is used to simulate the proposed 6G-based IoMT framework. The network parameter details were given in Table 1. This setup consists of 100 nodes,

randomly deployed over a 100 x 100 m² area. Each node has random mobility, and the cluster head is selected using the proposed HMO-SF-WSO cluster selection algorithm. The proposed 6G-enabled IoT framework has the following assumption:

- The mechanism proposed assumes all nodes except the sink have the ability to move (mobility) throughout the simulation.
- The wireless sensor nodes are considered to be IoMT nodes in the network with 6G communication capabilities, which enhance connectivity and data transfer efficiency.
- The IoMT devices operate with energy constraints, while the sink is assumed to operate without energy constraints.
- All nodes are assumed to have a different initial energy and holds 3-level heterogeneous energy capabilities.

In this work, the widely employed radio energy consumption model from the literature is used to transmit and receive data between 6G-enabled IoMT devices and sink nodes. Fig. 1 shows the IoMT network with 6G capabilities. The 6G-enabled IoMT network comprises devices installed in hospitals, homes, and ambulances that leverage 6G to deliver high-speed, low-latency connectivity. Fig 2 represents the general system model step of the proposed framework. The proposed mechanism begins with the arrangement of randomly distributed nodes with mobility.

Fig. 1. IoMT network with 6G capabilities

TABLE I. NETWORK PARAMETER DETAILS

Parameters	Values
Number of nodes used	100
Area	100 x 100
Base Station	50 x 50
Size of data packets	2000 bits
Node density ratio (normal, intermediate, advanced)	70%, 20%, and 10%
Initial energy of nodes (normal, intermediate, advanced)	1.0J, 1.50J and 2.0J

Fig. 2. General system model steps of the proposed mechanism

Afterward, required parameters, such as the system model parameter and the optimization algorithm parameter, are initialized. Subsequently, the 3-level heterogeneous energy model is initialized. Then, the proposed hybrid multi-objective starfish white shark optimization-based cluster selection algorithm is employed for energy-efficient routing. After selecting the optimal cluster heads, multi-hop cluster communication is established based on the shortest distance to the sink. Lastly, data transmission and reception were established between the node and the cluster head, and between the multi-hop cluster and the sink.

IV. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

The proposed energy-efficient routing protocol is inspired by two recent metaheuristic optimization algorithms, namely the starfish and white shark algorithms. The starfish optimization algorithm is a bio-inspired algorithm primarily designed to solve engineering-related problems. It stimulated

the starfish's exploration, preying, and regeneration behaviors. In the exploration stage, the starfish optimization algorithm uses a hybrid search pattern that combines five-dimensional and unidimensional search strategies to achieve high search capacity and efficiency, making it useful for solving multi-dimensional optimization problems. During the exploitation phase of the starfish optimization algorithm, a parallel two-directional search is used to update starfish positions, while a regeneration mechanism enhances global convergence and speed.

Conversely, the white shark optimization algorithm was also biologically inspired and designed to solve mainly engineering problems. Typically, sharks have unexpectedly sharp hearing, which helps them explore a wide area when searching for food. Furthermore, they have a sharp sense of smell, which helps them detect the scent of their prey. These characteristics allow sharks to travel throughout the entire search area and to utilize every possible part of it for food. After the exploitation and exploration phase, during the search phase to locate the prey, the shark exhibited three distinct behaviors: motion towards prey, an erratic hunt for prey in the depths of the ocean, and fish school behavior.

Additionally, these two recent optimization algorithms have distinct properties that enable them to address diverse applications. The recent starfish optimizer is a powerful tool with solid exploration and exploitation abilities but it is weak on balancing. To advance the search and exploitation capabilities of the starfish optimizer, this study proposes integrating the schooling behavior mechanism of the great white shark optimizer into the starfish optimization algorithm.

A. Proposed hybrid multi-objective starfish-white shark optimization (HMO-SF-WSO)-based energy efficient routing algorithm

The proposed energy-efficient routing protocol incorporates the strong behavior of both the SFOA and WSO protocols. Moreover, to extend the network's lifespan, we employed a multi-objective fitness function to select appropriate cluster heads. As mentioned previously, the starfish optimization algorithm has an excellent exploitation and exploration approach; however, it may face challenges in application-specific cluster head selection and feature selection. The starfish optimization algorithm may struggle to balance exploitation and exploration. To address this limitation starfish optimizer, we proposed a hybrid multi-objective starfish-white shark optimization for cluster head selection. This proposed algorithm employed the white shark's optimizer fish schooling behaviour to boost starfish optimization capabilities for better exploration and exploitation strategy. The pseudocode of the proposed HMO-SF-WSO energy-efficient routing algorithm is given in Algorithm. 1.

Algorithm 1: Proposed hybrid multi-objective starfish-white shark optimization cluster head selection

Input: Population size, Max iteration, Number of nodes (N)

Output: Optimal cluster heads

1. Initially, generate an initial population solution X randomly ranging between 0 and 1.
2. Convert this random population solution to binary format

$$X_{bin} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } X_i > 0.5 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Where $i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, N$

3. Compute the current best fitness function $best_{ff}$ and the best position $best_{pos}$ by using multi objective fitness function as per algorithm 2.
4. While $l \leq \text{Max iteration}$

For $k = 1$ to Population size

Phase 1: Exploration of SFOA

The new position was determined by using

$$\hat{X}_k = \begin{cases} X_k + p_m (best_{pos} - X_k) \cos \theta & \text{if } rand \leq 0.5 \\ X_k + p_m (best_{pos} - X_k) \sin \theta & \text{if } rand > 0.5 \end{cases}$$

Where

$$p_m = (2 * rand - 1) \pi$$

$$\theta = \frac{\pi}{2} * \frac{l}{\text{Max iteration}}$$

Update the boundary conditions by using

$$\hat{X}_k = \begin{cases} \hat{X}_k & lb < \hat{X}_k < ub \\ X_k & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Phase 2: Exploitation of SFOA

Compute the distance

$$dm1 = (best_{pos} - X_r)$$

where $r = 1$ to 5

Update the starfish's preying behavior by using

$$\hat{X}_k = \hat{X}_k + rand1 dm1 + rand2 dm2$$

Update the starfish's regeneration phase positions by using

$$\hat{X}_k = \exp\left(-l \frac{N}{\text{Max iteration}}\right) * \hat{X}_k$$

Update the boundary conditions by using

$$\hat{X}_k = \begin{cases} \hat{X}_k & lb < \hat{X}_k < ub \\ lb & \hat{X}_k < lb \\ ub & \hat{X}_k > lb \end{cases}$$

Phase 3: White shark's fish schooling behavior

The shark's fish school behavior was determined by using

$$\hat{X}_k = \frac{\hat{X}_k + best_{pos} + rand * D * \text{sgn}(rand - 0.5)}{2 * rand}$$

Where $D = |rand * (best_{pos} - 1 * \hat{X}_k)|$

End

For $k = 1$ to Population size

Compute fitness function (*new fit*) for a new position

If *new fit* > *fit* (k)

$fit(k) = new\ fit$

$X_k = \hat{X}_k$

if *new fit* > *gobal best*

gobal best = *fit* (k)

$best_{pos} = \hat{X}_k$

end

End While

5. Determine the optimal cluster head by performing binary conversion on *gobal best*

$S_{CH} = gobal\ best > 0.5$

Algorithm 1 starts with a random initial population, and then, according to step 2, converts the population into a binary format. In step 3 computed best fitness function and best position were computed by using algorithm 2. After computing the fitness function main loop started. The new position was computed by SFOA 's exploitation equation, and then the boundary condition was checked and updated. In the exploration stage, there are 2 distinct types of search techniques, including five directional and unidirectional search methods. In this study, we utilized five directional search mechanisms for the exploration phase. Conversely, during the exploitation phase, two search techniques are employed: bidirectional and unidirectional search methods. In this phase, a new position was computed based on the starfish's preying behavior and the regeneration of the starfish. Once again, boundary conditions were checked and updated. Following this SFOA exploration and exploitation phase, the schooling behavior of white sharks was implemented to enhance SFOA's exploration and exploitation skills. The exploration and exploitation process of these SFOAs, and the schooling behavior of the WSO, were repeatedly performed for all the search agents. Subsequently, the fitness function of the new position was computed by using Algorithm 2. If the (*new fit*) function is better than the previous fitness function (*fit*), the new fitness function and positions were updated, and if the current fitness function is better than the global fitness function (*gobal best*) the new fitness function is considered as the global fitness function and its respective position is considered as the best position ($best_{pos}$). These steps 4 are repeated until it reaches maximum iteration, and finally, the optimal cluster head selected index was computed by performing binary conversation on the global best position.

Algorithm 2: Multi-objective fitness function

Input: selected cluster head index, nodes' position, and remaining energy details

Output: *new fit*

The multi-objective fitness function has four distinct types of fitness functions to estimate the selected cluster heads.

1. Fitness function 1: Residual energy

$$FF_1 = \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{RE_i}{IE_i}$$

2. Fitness function 2: Energy level of node remaining

$$FF_2 = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N RE_i$$

3. Fitness function 3: Cluster's Energy

$$FF_3 = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^{NCH} RE_i$$

4. Fitness function 4: Node and sink distance

$$FF_4 = \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{DS_{node\ to\ sink_i}}{AvgDS_{node\ to\ sink_i}}$$

$new\ fit = a1 * FF_1 + a2 * FF_2 + a3 * FF_3 + a4 * FF_4$

Algorithm 2 represents the pseudocode of the proposed multi-objective fitness function to estimate the selected cluster heads. In this work, we employed 4 fitness functions, such as residual energy, residual energy levels of nodes, cluster's energy, and node and base station distance. In fitness function 1, the ratio of residual energy (RE_i) to initial energy IE_i was computed. The remaining energy level of the remaining node was considered in fitness function 2, and the energy of the selected cluster head was considered in fitness function 3. Finally, the distance of a candidate node from the sink ($DS_{node\ to\ sink_i}$) relative to the average distance of all nodes from the sink $AvgDS_{node\ to\ sink_i}$. Based on this fitness function, the final fitness is computed by using

$new\ fit = a1 * FF_1 + a2 * FF_2 + a3 * FF_3 + a4 * FF_4$

Where $a1$, $a2$, $a3$, and $a4$ are random number and the sum of these random numbers should be 1.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section observes the performance analysis of the proposed energy storage cluster formation algorithm, and it is compared with other baseline algorithms such as Grey Wolf Optimization (GWO), Whale Optimization Algorithm (WOA), Red Tail Hawk optimization (RTH), Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO), and Star Fish Optimization Algorithm (SFOA). The performance analysis of the energy-efficient methods was conducted based on network lifespan,

throughput, residual energy, and packet delivery ratio. Fig. 3 and Fig. 4 show the 6 G-enabled IoMT multi-hop cluster head routing scenario. In approximately the 1677th round, the first node dies in the proposed routing algorithm. Fig. 5 illustrates the network lifetime across rounds for the proposed and existing approaches. Our proposed cluster-head selection routing algorithm outperformed baseline routing algorithms.

Fig. 3. 6G enabled IoMT Multi-hop cluster head to cluster head routing - Round -25 (No dead node)

Fig. 4. 6G enabled IoMT Multi-hop cluster head to cluster head routing - Round -1677 (1st dead node)

Fig. 5. Performance Evaluation of Network Lifetime Across Rounds for Proposed and Existing Methods

It indicates the technique we proposed attained 81.48%, 44.11%, 36.11%, 8.88% and 6.52% increased network life span while compared to PSO, GWO, RTH, WOA, and SFOA optimization algorithms. Compared to the existing SFOA and WOA algorithms, the proposed routing algorithms maintains.

100% node survival up to 1500 rounds

Fig. 6. Performance Evaluation of Throughput Across Rounds for Proposed and Existing Methods

Fig. 7. Performance Evaluation of Packet Delivery Ratio Across Rounds for Proposed and Existing Methods

Fig. 8. Performance Evaluation of Residual Energy Across Rounds for Proposed and Existing Methods

Fig. 6 represents the throughput across rounds for the proposed and existing methods. Due to consistent energy availability across all nodes, all methods exhibit a comparable throughput trend in the first few rounds. The proposed routing algorithm maintains higher throughput as the number of rounds increases, demonstrating effective data transfer and balanced energy consumption. On the other hand, node failures and excessive energy consumption gradually degrade the efficiency of existing methods. The proposed routing algorithm shows better stability in subsequent rounds, demonstrating its ability to maintain network performance over prolonged operation.

Fig. 7 represents the packet delivery ratio across rounds for the proposed and existing methods. The stable packet delivery ratio observed for the proposed technique is due to the sustained node stability throughout the rounds. As node failures increase over time, the PDR of the existing mechanisms declines. Fig. 8 represents the remaining energy across rounds for the proposed and existing approaches. When the number of rounds increases, the energy reduction rate of the proposed routing method decreases, indicating

efficient energy utilization and balanced load distribution. As mentioned previously, each node has a different starting energy level to establish a 6G network connection. Our proposed cluster head selection method consumes much less energy over simulation rounds than current methods.

VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORKS AND DISCUSSION

In this work, we presented a hybrid multi-objective starfish white shark optimization algorithm for energy-efficient communication for 6G-enabled IoMT devices. Our technique adopts a mobility node and multi-cluster communication to enhance the stability of the 6G network. The proposed cluster head routing mechanism was inspired by two recent algorithms, namely the starfish and white shark optimization algorithms. The starfish optimization algorithm has excellent exploitation and exploration capabilities; however, it may encounter challenges in other applications, such as cluster selection and feature selection. To boost the performance of the starfish optimization algorithm in terms of exploration and exploitation white shark optimization algorithm was used. The experimental findings determine that our proposed cluster-head algorithm maintains 49 alive nodes, which is better than existing routing algorithms such as PSO, GWO, RTH, WOA, and SFOA. Notably, our proposed cluster-head-selection method achieved 43.75% lower energy consumption than the grey wolf optimization algorithm. Finally, our proposed cluster-head-selection technique achieved a 27.5% less energy consumption compared to baseline methods. Future work will attempt to rise the number of node deployments and node activation actions, permitting effective operation in large-scale network configurations.

REFERENCES

- [1] Mathkor, D.M., et al., Multirole of the internet of medical things (IoMT) in biomedical systems for managing smart healthcare systems: An overview of current and future innovative trends. *Journal of Infection and Public Health*, 2024. 17(4): p. 559–572.
- [2] Chen, J., et al., Wireless 6G cloud communication based security analysis using machine learning in Internet of Medical Things (IoMT). *Wireless Personal Communications*, 2024: p. 1–10.
- [3] Elaziz, M.A., et al., Medical image classifications for 6G IoT-enabled smart health systems. *Diagnostics*, 2023. 13(5): p. 834.
- [4] Wang, W., et al., An integrated deep learning algorithm for detecting lung nodules with low-dose CT and its application in 6G-enabled internet of medical things. *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, 2020. 8(7): p. 5274–5284.
- [5] Ramu, K., et al., Modern diagnostic imaging classifications and risk factors for 6G-enabled smart health systems. *Radioelectronics and Communications Systems*, 2023. 66(5): p. 241–250.
- [6] Subramaniam, E.V.D., et al., Interoperable IoMT approach for remote diagnosis with privacy-preservation perspective in edge systems. *Sensors*, 2023. 23(17): p. 7474.
- [7] Yuvarani, R., et al., Energy-aware cluster head optimization and secure blockchain integration for heterogeneous 6G-enabled IoMT networks. *Scientific Reports*, 2025. 15(1): p. 30009.
- [8] Malik, A., et al., Optimizing secure data transmission in 6g-enabled iomt using blockchain integration. *IEEE Transactions on Consumer Electronics*, 2024.
- [9] Al -Baz, A. and A. El -Sayed, A new algorithm for cluster head selection in LEACH protocol for wireless sensor networks. *International journal of communication systems*, 2018. 31(1): p. e3407.
- [10] Gupta, P. and A.K. Sharma, Clustering-based heterogeneous optimized-HEED protocols for WSNs. *Soft Computing*, 2020. 24(3): p. 1737–1761.
- [11] Zhong, C., et al., Starfish optimization algorithm (SFOA): a bio-inspired metaheuristic algorithm for global optimization compared with 100 optimizers. *Neural Computing and Applications*, 2025. 37(5): p. 3641–3683.
- [12] Braik, M., et al., White Shark Optimizer: A novel bio-inspired metaheuristic algorithm for global optimization problems. *Knowledge-Based Systems*, 2022. 243: p. 108457.
- [13] Anguraj, D.K., et al., Enriched cluster head selection using augmented bifold cuckoo search algorithm for edge-based internet of medical things. *International Journal of Communication Systems*, 2021. 34(9): p. e4817.
- [14] Rajalingam, R., K. Kavitha, and M. Anu, A Smart Healthcare System for IOMT using an Ant-Colony Optimized Centroid-Based Hybrid Protocol with Cluster-Centric Energy Efficient Routing in WSN-Assisted IOT. *International Journal of Communication Networks and Information Security*, 2024. 16(3): p. 223–236.
- [15] Jha, R.R., et al. Development of energy efficient routing protocol using genetic algorithm for IoMT. in *2023 Third International Conference on Secure Cyber Computing and Communication (ICSCCC)*. 2023. IEEE.